

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

ARTEMIS

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Description of the agroecological farm network and the initial monitoring in a harmonized database

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Executive summary

The ARTEMIS project, part of the EJP SOIL project, aims to improve our understanding of how agroecological (AE) systems impact soil health, thereby supporting the transition to more climate-resilient agroecosystems. Work Package 5 (WP5) specifically focuses on establishing a network of AE farms and developing a harmonised monitoring framework to evaluate the effects of AE practices on soil health and soil-related ecosystem services (ESS).

In this report, we introduce an AE farm network that has been established in collaboration with six project partners, representing various land uses, AE systems, and pedo-climatic conditions. The AE farm network served as a test case for the on-farm monitoring framework developed within ARTEMIS and has provided preliminary data on soil health indicators such as soil organic carbon (SOC), pH, and bulk density. The monitoring framework has proven effective for harmonised data collection across different countries, fostering collaboration among research partners. Preliminary results have indicated a high variability in soil indicators across the various sites, underscoring the challenges inherent in on-farm research due to the diversity of conditions. No significant differences were observed between AE plots and reference fields, indicating a need for further analysis that accounts for pedo-climatic differences between sites.

To thoroughly assess the impact of AE systems on soil health and ESS across Europe, it is necessary to expand the AE farm network, increase the number of farms, and focus on specific land uses and similar crops to promote meaningful comparisons. By incorporating additional farms and utilising the comprehensive monitoring framework and database, future research can provide more tailored AE solutions that address local needs and regional preferences. This approach will ultimately contribute to the development of more sustainable and resilient agricultural systems throughout Europe.

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Introduction

The ARTEMIS project sought to enhance our understanding of how specific agroecological (AE) systems influence the soil's capacity to mitigate and alleviate the effects of climate change. Work Package 5 (WP5) focused on creating a network of AE farms dedicated to improving soil health and harnessing soil-related ESS. In the next step, the WP5 developed monitoring framework will be employed to assess the impact of various AE systems on soil health and soil-related ecosystem services (ESS). Additionally, a comprehensive database will be created and maintained to store the monitoring data. The report will present an overview of the established AE farm network, introduce the newly developed database, and offer preliminary insights into the effects of AE systems on several indicators of soil health.

Objectives

To leverage the advantages of on-farm research, we aimed to establish an AE farm network across Europe, spanning various pedo-climatic conditions represented by the project partners. The farms could be managed by innovative farmers or also be experimental site management by research staff to exemplify the benefit of AE management, all of them possibly yielding as lighthouse farms in future projects. This initial network aimed to reflect the diverse regional implementations of AE systems and test harmonised soil health monitoring. The establishment of the AE farm network aligns with the objectives of The Mission "A Soil Deal for Europe," which aims to create 100 Living Labs and Lighthouses to facilitate the transition toward healthy soils (EU Commission, 2022). This initiative underscores the crucial role of living labs and lighthouse farms in promoting sustainable soil management and expediting the shift to healthy, resilient soils throughout Europe.

In collaboration with the project partners AGRIS, AGROSCOPE, CSIC, ENEA, ERSAF, and ILVO, we envisioned establishing an initial set of AE farms by building on the existing contacts of the project partners with innovative farms practicing a spectrum of AE approaches—from organic farming to conservation agriculture and agroforestry.

The established AE farm network will serve as the initial setting for implementing and evaluating the proposed monitoring framework. This includes testing the feasibility of the suggested direct and indirect indicators for soil health and related ecosystem services, as well as managing the data storage within the framework of the WP5 established database. The ARTEMIS farm network should further serve as the first step toward establishing soil living labs dedicated to AE systems across Europe. Such a larger and more comprehensive AE farm network would be required to assess innovative AE practices across different pedo-climatic and socio-economic conditions in Europe. This would allow for tailoring these practices to meet local needs and enhance the resilience of agricultural systems across Europe. Due to limited resources, this is not currently feasible within the scope of ARTEMIS.

The ARTEMIS farm network

Figure 1 Map of Europe displaying all partner countries and their respective farms participating in the ARTEMIS farm network.

The established AE farm network consisted of 14 farmer-managed farms and two long-term field trial sites in four countries coordinated by six project partners (Fig. 1). By harnessing existing contacts of project partners with AE farms, the ARTEMIS farm network faces a considerable diversity in land uses, AE principles addressed, AE systems employed, and the AE practices applied in the lighthouse farms. Despite this, there were some often shared characteristics to be found within the established farm network. Most of the farms were engaged in arable cropland. The established AE farm network primarily focuses on the AE principles of diversity, ecological intensification, recycling and resource use efficiency, and soil health. However, the socio-economic implications of AE systems such as co-creation and social and economic equity have only marginally been addressed. The main AE systems embraced by the network are organic farming and conservation agriculture, supplemented by agroforestry. Within the farm network, several AE practices dominated, including diversification of crop rotation, cover cropping, green manure, reduced tillage, and integrated pest management. In the following, we present the participating farms coordinated by the different project partners.

Description of Participating Agroecological Lighthouse Farms

Agroecological Farms in North-West Spain

The farm network, coordinated by CSIC, comprises three farms from the province of Ourense and A Coruña, Spain. All farms emphasise diversity, soil health, recycling, and resource use efficiency as AE principles to enhance resilience and ecosystem services. The farms vary in land use, including vineyards and arable cropland, and all are managed by farmers, with no replication of agroecological treatments across the sites. Cambisol is the dominant soil type in this region, and it is influenced by Atlantic and Mediterranean climates.

The second farm, Casa Grande de Xanceda, is situated in Mesía and focuses on arable cropland with ley-grasslands in rotation with rainfed forage maize. With 20 years of AE practices, it also follows organic farming. Key agroecological practices include integrated pest management, intercropping, cover cropping, and diversified crop rotation.

The fourth farm, D'Aiquí, in Rairiz de Veiga, operates in horticulture. This site has been engaged in AE practices for 34 years, utilising an agroforestry and polyculture system. Key practices include cover cropping, green manure, and reduced tillage.

Additionally, the D'Aiquí farm operates in cereal production, providing a second site for the farm network. This field has also been practising agroecology for 34 years, employing a conservation agriculture and agroforestry-based system. Key practices include diversified crop rotation, cover cropping, green manure, and integrated pest management.

Lastly, the MIMA farm in Meire features horticulture and has been employing agroecological practices for 10 years. The farm follows an agroforestry and polyculture system, with key practices including reduced tillage, diversified crop rotation, and integrated pest management.

Agroecological Long-Term Experimental Sites in Sardinia, Italy

The AE sites in Sardinia, Italy, are coordinated by AGRIS and belong to long-Term field experiments (LTE). The sites encompass 2 hectares each and include three replications for each treatment. They emphasise resilience and adaptation, as well as recycling and resource use efficiency, as AE principles. The farms operate under a Mediterranean climate.

The first site is located in Ussana and features Petrocalcic Palexeralf soil (medium/medium-low fertility). It has been engaged in an LTE on conservation agriculture for 20 years. Key practices at this site include diversified crop rotation and reduced tillage.

The second site is located in Benatzu and consists of Vertic Epiaquept soil (medium-high/high fertility). Similar to the site in Ussana, it has also been involved in an LTE on conservation agriculture for 20 years. Key practices at this site include diversified crop rotation and reduced tillage.

Agroecological Farm in Bologna, Italy

The AE farm Spazio Battirame is managed by the social cooperative ETA-Beta and is located in Bologna, Italy. The farm emphasises diversity, ecological intensification, recycling and resource use efficiency, soil health, co-creation, and social and economic equity as fundamental AE principles. The farm encompasses approximately 4 hectares and operates under a humid subtropical climate. It features sandy clay loam soil. The farm has been operational for seven years and is managed by farmers under the scientific supervision of researchers.

The farm is engaged in AE approaches, including intercropping vegetables, aromatic herbs, and fruit trees alongside uncropped and functional biodiversity areas under a conservation agriculture and organic farming-based system. Key agroecological practices include diversified crop rotation, cover cropping, green manure, intercropping, reduced tillage, and biological pest control.

Agroecological Farms in Lombardy, Italy

Three farms from Lombardy, Italy, could contribute to the AE farm network coordinated by ERSAF. All farms follow mainly conservation agriculture principles, which aim to promote resilience and adaptation by designing systems capable of addressing environmental challenges, such as climate change. Each farm spans approximately 5 hectares and is managed by a farmer, with no replication of AE treatments across the sites. In these farms, the CSA climate —characterised by hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters—requires management to cope with seasonal droughts and rainy winter months.

The first farm, Az. Agricola Grandi Umberto, is located in Barbianello on clay/loam soil. This arable cropland has been managed following agroecological principles since 2014. Key practices at the site include crop rotation, cover cropping, and reduced tillage.

The second farm, Az. Agricola Rossi, is situated in Malagnino on silty-loam soil. A conservation agricultural system has been in place since 2014, focusing on diversified crop rotation, cover cropping, and no-till/reduced tillage.

The third farm, Az. Agricola Dellabona is located in Gambara, where the soil varies from sandy loam to silty clay. This site employs diversified crop rotation and reduced tillage as part of its AE management.

Agroecological Farms in Central Plateau, Switzerland

Two Swiss farms are part of the AE farm network coordinated by Agroscope. These farms prioritise diversity, soil health, recycling, and resource use efficiency as agroecological principles on their arable cropland. The farms are independently managed by farmers, and there is no replication of AE treatments across the sites. The predominant soil type in this region is Cambisol, and the area experiences a mild continental climate.

The first farm, Dupraz, is located in Meinier. This farm has been practising AE principles for 10 years, following organic farming as its AE system. Key AE practices at this site include agroforestry and integrated pest management. The farm employs diversified crop rotation, cover cropping, reduced tillage and green manure to enhance soil health.

The second farm, Strickler-Gwerder, is situated in Menzingen. This site has been engaged in AE practices for 50 years, employing organic farming as a system approach. Key AE practices here include agroforestry and biological pest control. To improve soil health, the farm employs diversified crop rotation, cover cropping, no-till and intercropping.

Agroecological Farms in Flanders, Belgium

Four farms from Belgium contribute to the ARTEMIS AE farm network coordinated by ILVO. All farms emphasise diversity, soil health, recycling, and resource use efficiency as AE principles. The farms vary in land use, including arable cropland, agroforestry, and horticulture, and are managed by farmers, with no replication of AE treatments across the sites. The dominant soil types in this region include sandy loam, sand and clay, influenced by a temperate maritime climate.

The first farm, Project Hansbeke Agro-ecologie (PHAE), is situated in Hansbeke (Deinze) and focuses on arable cropland, with 5 years of AE management under organic farming. Key AE practices include polyculture, diversified crop rotation, cover cropping, biological pest control, and compost application.

The second farm, DE LEVENDE AARDE, located in Oostkamp, operates in horticulture. This farm has been engaged in AE practices for 10 years, utilising organic farming as its system approach. Key AE practices include reduced tillage, diversified crop rotation, green manure, cover cropping, and integrated pest management, focusing on maximising the use of resources within the farm system.

The third farm, Hof Ter Meulen, in Vlissegem (De Haan), practices arable farming, animal husbandry and agroforestry. This site has been operational for 5 years, following an organic farming system approach. Key practices include diversified crop rotation, reduced tillage, and intercropping, emphasising the integration of trees or woody shrubs with agricultural crops.

The fourth site, the farm of Stijn Dewulf and Charlotte Nuytten, located in Ledegem, focuses on arable cropland. This farm has been practising AE principles for four years, employing conservation agriculture. Key AE practices include cover cropping, reduced tillage green manure, and diversified crop rotation.

Existing Agroecological Living Labs and On-Farm Initiatives in the Partner Countries

As the newly established AE farm network serves as the first step in building a more comprehensive and harmonised AE farm network for the future, we also collected information about existing AE living labs or AE initiatives that could complement the existing network with additional suitable farms. This will provide a good setting for establishing the basis for on-farm research on the influence of AE approaches on soil health and soil-related agroecosystems. The AE living labs and initiatives in the partner countries are described below.

Asociación de Viticultura Regenerativa

The *Asociación de Viticultura Regenerativa* (viticulturnaregenerativa.org), established in Spain in 2021, is dedicated to promoting sustainable viticultural practices. This initiative aims to equip viticulturists with the necessary tools to implement regenerative practices. The association organises events like symposiums, workshops, and field visits and publishes newsletters to promote regenerative viticulture. It involves 65 wine producers and five individual participants dedicated to sustainable vineyard management. Practices advocated include reduced tillage, crop rotation, and maintaining permanent soil cover to improve soil health.

The Futuro Viñador initiative

Futuro Viñador is an initiative in Spain to recover and celebrate ancestral viticultural practices and the rich diversity of native ancient grape varieties. The initiative highlights the importance of biodiversity and seeks to conserve the functionality of viticultural landscapes. *Futuro Viñador* organises meetings for viticulturists, facilitating the sharing of experiences. Additionally, it produces publications to practical information about traditional practices. Currently, 16 viticulturists are actively involved in the initiative. Key AE practices endorsed by *Futuro Viñador* are linked to conservation agriculture.

Sociedad Española de Agricultura Ecológica y Agroecología

The *Sociedad Española de Agricultura Ecológica y Agroecología* (SEAE; agroecologia.net) has been promoting organic agriculture and agroecology in Spain since its inception in 2019. The organisation works collaboratively with farmers and researchers. The SEAE focuses on workshops, seminars, meetings, and publications. The SEAE extends to 145 organisations, collectives, and 752 individuals, illustrating its extensive network and influence within the agricultural community.

The SEAE's mission is centred around promoting biodiversity, ecological intensification, and resource use efficiency. Soil health is a major focus, emphasising practices that avoid synthetic chemicals and instead focus on natural fertilisers and pest control methods. The SEAE also strongly emphasises social and economic equity, ensuring that benefits and resources are distributed fairly among farmers and communities.

The ASSIOLO Project

The *ASSIOLO project*, organised by AGRIS Sardegna, aims to facilitate the transition to agroecology for farmers and citizens alike. To accomplish this, ASSIOLO has established a collaborative partnership involving farmers, tourism operators, restaurants, traders, and residents of Villamassargia. The project encompasses a wide range of agricultural areas, including horticulture, olive groves, arable cropland, permanent grassland, orchards, and vineyards. ASSIOLO promotes AE principles such as ecological intensification, recycling, and resource use efficiency, with a strong focus on soil health advocating for adopting organic farming practices. ASSIOLO emphasises the importance of co-creation by actively engaging local farmers and communities in decision-making and knowledge-sharing processes.

Living Lab Mediterranean Agricultural Soils

The Living Lab *Mediterranean Agricultural Soils* established within the *InBestSoil* project under Horizon Europe, is a collaborative initiative co-led by Agris Sardegna and the CMCC Foundation. The Living Lab comprises two lighthouse sites and nine additional experimental sites, engaging around 20 farmers. The primary objective of this Living Lab is to evaluate AE practices, with a particular emphasis on conservation agriculture as a potential solution for climate change adaptation and mitigation. To achieve this goal, the living lab fosters co-creation, co-innovation, and co-learning activities among its diverse stakeholder community. It focuses on monitoring and evaluating conservation agricultural practices.

The Romagna Biosymbiotic District Initiative

The *Romagna Biosymbiotic District*, launched in 2016, involves farmers from Italy's Emilia Romagna Region. Its main goal is to provide a sustainable income for farmers practising biodiversity-based farming while also promoting the health and cultural well-being of the local community. The initiative includes establishing a certification scheme for bio-symbiotic agriculture, which encourages the integration of beneficial microorganisms into farming practices. With approximately 50 participating farms, the district encompasses arable cropland, permanent grassland, horticulture, vineyards, and forested areas. The focus on ecological intensification is geared towards enhancing agricultural productivity and optimising resource use efficiency by effectively utilising beneficial interactions between living organisms in agroecosystems, organic matter, water, and nutrients.

Living Lab Innovative and Sustainable Models for Soil Health

The Living Lab *Innovative and Sustainable Models for Soil Health*, initiated by ERSAF in collaboration with The Catholic University of the Sacred Heart in Piacenza and The University of Milan, is based in the Po Valley area of Northern Italy. Established in May 2022, this ongoing initiative focuses on developing and transferring sustainable soil management practices tailored to the local context. To achieve its goals, the Living Lab engages in various activities, including soil health monitoring in selected farms, education and training initiatives, field visits to lighthouse farms for knowledge exchange, and communication activities to foster collaboration among participants. The Living Lab brings together a diverse group of 28 participants and emphasises the co-creation of sustainable management practices to promote soil health. At the core of its approach are the principles of *Conservation Agriculture*, which focus on minimal soil disturbance, cover cropping, and crop rotation to enhance soil health and reduce erosion.

The Living Soil Initiative

The *Living Soil Initiative* (solvivants.org), established by the Earthworm Foundation and based in Switzerland, was launched in 2022 and remains active. The main objective of this initiative is to cultivate healthy soils as the cornerstone of a sustainable food system. It advocates for a collaborative approach involving all value chain stakeholders, including farmers, agri-food companies, distributors, scientists, policymakers, shareholders, and agronomists. The initiative is structured around 12 Living Labs, where practical principles implementations are tested and refined in partnership with farmers. Key practices involve promoting the diversity of agroecosystems and maximising the use of resources within the farm system by encouraging beneficial interactions between different components, such as crops and livestock. The primary goals include improving soil health through regenerative practices and promoting conservation agriculture, which encompasses minimal soil disturbance, crop rotation, and using permanent soil cover and green manure.

The Boden.Leben Association

Boden.Leben (bodenistleben.at) is an association primarily focused in Eastern Austria. Launched in April 2019, the ongoing association aims to advance knowledge through practice-oriented research while facilitating a dialogue between scientists and farmers. A core aspect of the initiative is co-creation, which involves engaging farmers and local communities in decision-making and knowledge-sharing processes. Boden.Leben advocates for Conservation Agriculture practices, specifically minimal soil disturbance, crop rotation, and permanent soil cover to enhance soil health. The association aims for climate-adapted and regenerative agriculture.

The PPAE Hansbeke Experimental Platform for Agroecology

The Experimental Platform for Agroecology in Hansbeke (ppaehansbeke.be) is a collaborative effort involving the organic farmer Felix de Bousies from the PHAE farm, ILVO, and agricultural consultant and researcher Alain Peeters from RHEA. Located in Flanders, Belgium, this initiative aims to generate

and disseminate expertise on applying AE principles, including reduced tillage, on-farm composting, agroforestry, and circular livestock farming, alongside mixed cultures. The farm serves as a potential lighthouse for demonstrating these innovative techniques.

Living Lab for Agroecology and Organic Agriculture

The Living Lab for Agroecology and Organic Agriculture (LLAEBIO, <https://llaebio.be/>), coordinated by ILVO in Flanders, Belgium, aims to support the sustainability of the agri-food system and act as a facilitator of this growth process. To this end, it supports and guides the interested actors from organic and/or conventional agriculture in developing and exchanging innovative knowledge on AE practices. This living lab emphasises the importance of building partnerships between stakeholders, including authorities, organisations and farmers, to facilitate knowledge transfer, support research and innovation, research and novation and encourage co-creation.

Harmonised template for collecting soil health monitoring data

Within ARTEMIS, a template was created for both the collection and storage of the monitoring (meta)data coming from the proposed monitoring framework (ARTEMIS D5.1 (Panagea et.al, 2024)) as well as for storing farm management data that are required for estimation of the indirect indicators, the interpretation of the monitoring results and analysis. The template is available in the ARTEMIS zenodo community ((Panagea and Vanderhasselt, 2024) 10.5281/zenodo.13945225). For the template, we have started from the format and coding of the EJPSOIL SoilX management data template (Heller et al., 2024), the EJPSOIL LTE metadata template from Blanchy et al. (2023) the SoilCare database template (Panagea et al., 2021) but made some modification to cover the needs and requirements of the ARTEMIS on-farm monitoring framework.

Description of the template

The template follows the format of a relational database. When farmers make use of it, management information could be extracted from Farm Management Information Systems (FMIS), which exist for both commercial and scientific reasons. In the future, the Artemis template could be connected to FMIS (both for extracting management and for providing monitoring info to the FMIS), as each entry is recorded with unique IDs and combinations of IDs as in relational databases.

The template includes the following tabs:

ReadMe: Includes the license, references and instructions about the use of the template,

Field_into: Information about the fields of the farms monitored

Plots: Information about the sampling plots where the actual measurements took place

Data_management: Information about the management activities in the different fields

Data_soil: Quantitative results of the soil properties and indicators

Data_crop: Information about the crop, crop yield and biomass

Data_organic: Information about the quality of the organic material (optional)

Documents: Information about existing documents about the fields/farms etc. (papers, publications, etc.)

Observations_metadata: metadata about the methods and tools used for the analysis of each soil property or indicator

Description Management: Description of the management options and their source

Choice_list: Predefined lists of the different management categories.

Preliminary Results from the On-Farm Soil health Monitoring

In the frame of ARTEMIS, we conducted preliminary testing of the soil health monitoring framework and the established database within the AE farm network. Due to time constraints and limited data availability, preliminary data analysis faced challenges: not all sites were represented, and several soil parameters were missing. The preliminary data analysis focused, therefore, on soil health indicators with more than 20 data points in the topsoil, along with corresponding texture data. This allowed us to include soil organic carbon (SOC), total nitrogen (N), available phosphorus (P), potassium (K), pH, cation exchange capacity (CEC), and electrical conductivity (EC) in our analysis. The preliminary analysis compared AE fields with reference fields (where available) that lacked AE-specific treatments. We utilized a straightforward multivariate model that incorporated soil texture prior to evaluating system effects. This assessment was conducted using a hierarchical linear model (Type I Error), represented by the equation $y = \text{clay} + \text{sand} + \text{system}$. In this context, y refers to the soil health indicator being measured, while the term "system" signifies the comparison between AE fields and reference plots.

Figure 2 Boxplots with individual data points for available soil health indicators, comparing reference and agroecological fields within the ARTEMIS farm network. All soil health indicators with more than 20 data points in the topsoil were considered for the analysis, including soil organic carbon (SOC), total nitrogen (N), available phosphorus (P), potassium (K), pH, cation exchange capacity (CEC), and electrical conductivity (EC). F and p values for the system effect, derived from a multivariate model accounting for soil texture, are presented at the top of each plot.

The analysis showed no significant differences between the AE field and the reference field for any of the tested soil health variables (Fig. 2). The soil health indicators displayed considerable variability among the AE farms across six different partner countries, underscoring the importance of interpreting results within their specific pedo-climatic contexts. In the preliminary analysis, we only accounted for soil texture, which was for several of the tested soil health indicators a significant driver. By incorporating additional environmental variables, such as mean annual temperature and mean annual precipitation, we could potentially reduce the masking effect of environmental variability further and better reveal the effects of AE on soil health (Walder et al., 2023). Further analysis will be necessary once more comprehensive data, including these environmental parameters, become available.

Future efforts should prioritize expanding and refining the farm network to more effectively evaluate the impact of AE systems across varying environments. For instance, more targeted monitoring should focus on specific land uses and aim to evaluate the same or similar crop types wherever feasible consistently. This approach would allow for more accurate comparisons of AE management effects,

providing insights into how these practices perform in different soil types, climates, and agricultural contexts.

While the preliminary data analysis encountered challenges due to time constraints and incomplete data availability, the underlying database and monitoring framework demonstrated significant value. The framework's standardized data collection protocols and storage capabilities facilitated consistent data entry across countries and research partners, enabling efficient collaboration in on-farm research. Furthermore, this harmonized approach to data collection sets a foundation for longitudinal studies and cross-country analyses, which are essential for understanding the broader impacts of AE systems.

Summary

We established an AE farm network across the six WP partners, with 2 to 5 farms per partner, to monitor the effects of AE systems on soil health. The network demonstrated high diversity in land use and AE practices, reflecting the many ways AE systems can shape agricultural management. However, the preliminary results highlight the challenges of on-farm research, as the wide range of pedo-climatic conditions led to considerable variability in the soil health indicators assessed. Expanding the AE farm network with additional farms remains to be a pertinent next step. To this end, we can leverage information on AE living labs and initiatives in participating countries gathered in the frame of the WP5 and outlined in the report. With an extensive AE farm network and the implementation of the developed monitoring framework, future research will be better positioned to analyze the impact of AE management in a context-specific manner. This will ultimately enable farms to customize AE practices to meet local needs and regional preferences.

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